

Comparison of Nonrelativistic Quantum and Newtonian Mechanics in terms of Information Suggesting the Latter is not a Limit of the Former

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In (1) we argued that one may derive Newton's second law (which is equivalent to an energy conservation equation) by using information arguments. We argued that $V(x)$, a potential, is a fixed piece of spatial information linked to the x axis being divided into equal dx units. The variable spatial information is $dt(x)$ i.e. the time spent in each dx or $v(x) = dx/dt$ (to put this in the same form as the time displacement generator). One may not simply compare $v(x)$ directly with $V(x)$ because they change differently. $v(x)$ changes in a weighted way i.e. $v(x)d/dx$ or d/dt while $V(x)$ changes as $d/dx V(x)$. Thus we suggest $d/dt v(x) = C V(x)$ which ultimately leads to Newton's second law. Using $d/dt \rightarrow v(x)d/dx$ and integrating yields conservation of energy: $p(x)p(x)/2m + V(x) = E$.

A similar argument was used in (2) to deal with the special relativistic case. There one cannot use $d/dt \rightarrow v(x)d/dx$ to obtain a conservation of energy equation. The point we wish to make is that for both the nonrelativistic and relativistic classical equations there are two types of "information" equations. The first is a "force" i.e. $-dV/dx$ equation which is based on how $V(x)$ changes with x . The LHS of this equation is linked to $d/dt p(x)$. The second is a corresponding energy conservation equation.

The quantum case is quite different, we argue, because a free particle is described by $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. There is still the notion of $p = m_0 dx/dt(x)$ as in the nonrelativistic case because p must be defined, but $\exp(ipx)$ is additional imposed piece of spatial information. $-id/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$ and $-d/dx d/dx \exp(ipx) = pp \exp(ipx)$.

This begs the question: How does one reconcile the two? For the nonrelativistic Newtonian and relativistic cases it is possible to have two equations (one with Force the other with energy) using one x dependent variable $p(x)$. In the quantum case one may take an average to define a kind of complex $\langle p \rangle = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ p \ \exp(ipx) / \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ \exp(ipx)$, but this is complex, not real. Furthermore both $+/-$ is included in $\langle p \rangle$ so there seems to be a problem linking it with changes in $V(x)$ in one direction. Thus it seems that one is forced to consider the second kind of information equation from classical mechanics and define a $\langle pp \rangle = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ pp \ \exp(ipx) / \{\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ \exp(ipx)\}$. In the nonrelativistic case this may be multiplied by $1/2m_0$ and then added to $V(x)$ to obtain a constant E . If one only looks at $\langle pp \rangle / 2m_0$ as a spatial function then this is identical to $KE(x)$ i.e. kinetic energy(x) for a classical system.

Thus in the nonrelativistic case, Newtonian energy conservation is always embedded in the quantum system regardless of the energy. In other words the quantum bound equation i.e. the time independent Schrodinger is not obtained independently from the classical one in terms of information. One may ask: How does information related to $\exp(ipx)$ affect the quantum system? Two immediate ways are as follows. First $\langle pp \rangle / 2m_0 = -1/2m_0 \ d/dx \ dW/dx / W$ where $W = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ \exp(ipx)$. This leads to a differential equation which has discrete E_n values verified by experiment. Secondly W is linked to spatial density $W^*(x)W(x)$ which exhibits crests and near zero regions. Using $\langle pp \rangle$ suggests that $p(x)$ in the classical case is linked to $p_{rms}(x)$ quantum. Thus building quantum mechanics using "informational" ideas seems to involve embedding

classical conservation of energy into the quantum equation a priori. This holds both nonrelativistically or relativistically (Klein-Gordon equation).

This immediately raises the question: If classical mechanics (in the form of energy conservation) is embedded in quantum mechanics for any energy, why do people seek to take some kind of limit (3) to obtain classical mechanics from quantum? We argue that quantum mechanics has more spatial information than classical, but retains classical conservation of energy so there is no limit to take. One may simply ignore ideas related to the wavelength to obtain classical mechanics, we argue.

A Conservation Equation From Invariant Changes in t-x

As noted above both nonrelativistic and relativistic mechanics may be described in terms of an “information” equation using derivatives i.e. $d/dt p(x) = -dV/dx$. d/dt and d/dx , however, are generators of changes in t and x and so it seems one seeks an invariant equation linked to changes in x, t . In other words one may write: $dp/dt + dV/dx = 0$ suggesting that changes of two pieces of information (one fixed $V(x)$) leads to 0 i.e. a kind of invariance.

These notions do only exist in classical mechanics, but already seem to be present in Fermat’s least time principle. In that case there is only one piece of information, namely overall time, for a reflecting/refracting light ray. Nevertheless one varies time to find an extremum. Mathematically this involves: $d/dx t_1(x) + t_2(x) = 0$. This operation, however, is identical to varying the “true solution” using the generator of an invariant variable d/dx . It is linked to the idea of spatial invariance in the x direction and leads to a conservation law because $dt_1/dx = -dt_2/dx$ is equivalent to: $(p_1x) = (p_2x)$ i.e. momentum conservation in the direction of the invariant variable.

In the case of nonrelativistic mechanics the “invariance” type equation involves two pieces of spatial information $p(x)$ and $V(x)$, not one of time(x), because $V(x)$ the potential is imposed on the system. The second piece of information $p(x)$ like time(x) in Fermat’s principle is variable and changes to minimize information, but in a weighted manner i.e. $d/dt \rightarrow v(x) d/dx$. In Fermat’s principle $(p_1x) = (p_2x)$ indicates that two pieces of information for momentum in the x direction are not needed, but only one.

A question which arises is: Can these same ideas be applied to quantum mechanics? We argue that matters are a little more complicated in such a case.

Quantum Mechanics

A fundamental part of quantum mechanics involves the description of a free particle by $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$. Considering the $\exp(ipx)$ piece alone indicates there exists more x information, namely the wavelength proportional to $1/p$, than only $p = \text{mod}x/dt(x)$ where $dt(x)$ happens to be constant. Newtonian mechanics only involves $dt(x) = \text{constant}$ for constant motion. Thus quantum and classical mechanics have different spatial information. In both, however, one imposes the same piece of spatial information namely $V(x)$, a potential.

In nonrelativistic/relativistic classical mechanics the response “information” is $p(x)$ which is $mv(x)$ in the nonrelativistic case and $mv(x)/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ in the relativistic. This variable piece of information’s behaviour under changes may be linked to the change of $V(x)$ i.e. dV/dx , but

$p(x)$ also appears in the energy conservation equation because it is obtained from $dp(x)/dt = -dV/dx$ one (although in different manners for the nonrelativistic and relativistic cases).

At first one might construct an average:

$$\langle p \rangle = \frac{\sum_p a(p) p \exp(ipx)}{\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)} = -idW/dx / W \quad \text{where } W = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx).$$

$W(x)$, however, is real for a bound quantum system so $\langle p \rangle$ is complex which is unphysical. Furthermore it contains both $+p$ and $-p$ averaged together while dV/dx only considers movement in one direction. Additionally $\langle p \rangle$ changes sign. Consider for example the ground state of a quantum oscillator. In classical mechanics one may have $x=0$ and $v=0$. A quantum average of $\exp(ipx)$'s, however, has some motion and if density is to be concentrated about $x=0$, $W(x)$ should be some kind of symmetric hump meaning $\langle p \rangle$ has a positive value on the LHS and a negative one on the RHS. Thus $\langle p \rangle$ does not seem to be a candidate for information linked with dV/dx .

A second average is:

$$\langle pp \rangle = \frac{\sum_p a(p) p^2 \exp(ipx)}{W(x)} = -d/dx dW/dx / W.$$

This is real and even though p and $-p$ are included this is fine because one computes an average kinetic energy i.e. $pp = (-p)(-p)$. As a result, in the nonrelativistic case one may link $\langle pp \rangle$ to the energy conservation (no x information at each x) equation. Then $p(x)$ classical is mapped to $prms(x)$ quantum (rather than $\langle p \rangle$). As a result an information equation from classical mechanics is directly utilized in quantum mechanics to establish an information relationship with the variable information piece $KE(x) = -d/dx dW/dx/W$. What are the implications of this?

First energy E becomes discrete and secondly W^*W , spatial density, displays humps not seen in classical mechanics. Thus $prms(x)$ and $KE(x)$ from any E_n level match classical values exactly, but one is restricted to certain E_n and there exists a density with humps not occurring in classical mechanics.

As a result, applying information to the quantum bound system is be done independently of classical mechanics. In other words, classical mechanical conservation of energy is embedded in every quantum energy level together with extra $\exp(ipx)$ spatial constraints.

Classical Mechanics as a Limit of Quantum Mechanics

It seems there has been interest in expressing classical mechanics as a limit of quantum mechanics for some time. In (3) it is argued that some have tried to consider an $\hbar \rightarrow 0$ limit. Procedures of using wave packets or Wigner's transformation have also been applied.

Based on the arguments above, classical mechanics is already embedded in every quantum bound state together with extra spatial information i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ s which does not exist in classical mechanics. Thus no limit needs to be taken to obtain classical mechanics. One simply needs to remove the effects of $\exp(ipx)$ information i.e. $W(x)$ and d/dx operators in the nonrelativistic quantum bound case, for example. The one has: $KE(x) + V(x) = E_n$ quantum mechanically. If

one ignores W and dW/dx , E_n 's are no longer discrete and $KE(x)$ may be considered in terms of $.5m v_{rms}(x)v_{rms}(x)$ which becomes $v(x)$ from the classical mechanical picture.

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that physics seems to include examples of "invariance" equations (i.e. equations including the generators $d/dx, d/dt$ and equaling 0) of certain pieces of information. For example, Fermat's least time principle for light (reflection/refraction etc) applies $d/dx (\text{time}_1(x) + \text{time}_2(x)) = 0$ where 1, 2 represent the incident and reflected/refracted rays. We argue that d/dx is a generator of displacement and that " $=0$ " means invariance in the spatial variable x . This is equivalent to a conservation equation namely $(p_1x) = (p_2x)$ where p is momentum.

For relativistic/nonrelativistic classical mechanics we argue that a $V(x)$ potential piece of spatial information is imposed. A variable piece of information, namely $p(x)$, must adjust such that there exists no "new or extra information" in the system. In other words changes in $p(x)$ must be linked to changes in $V(x)$ or $dp/dt = -dV/dx$ because dp/dx does not account for changes in $dt(x)$ in each constant dx . This then leads to a conservation of energy equation (although through different analyses for the relativistic and nonrelativistic cases) which in turn shows that at any x there is overall one piece of information E i.e. there exists a kind of equilibrium.

In this note we suggest that quantum mechanics has two imposed pieces of x information namely $V(x)$ and the form $\exp(ipx)$ from $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$. If one wishes to consider a bound problem as an equilibrium, one with time removed, then one focuses on $\exp(ipx)$. Following the classical scenario, one might consider $\langle p \rangle$ as equivalent to $p(x)$ where $\langle p \rangle = \{ \text{Sum over } p \text{ } p \text{ } a(p) \exp(ipx) \} / W(x)$, but this is complex, includes both p and $-p$ (in direct contrast to $p(x)$) and changes its sign in different regions of space even for a symmetric potential such as an oscillator. Thus even though $\langle p \rangle$ is a type of spatial information, it does not seem to be compatible with the imposed $V(x)$ in a simple manner.

We next consider $\langle pp \rangle$. This is real and there is no issue with $+p/-p$, but comparing with classical mechanics suggests $\langle pp \rangle$ should be associated with an energy conservation equation and not one with derivatives acting on $\langle pp \rangle$ and $V(x)$. This energy conservation equation, however, is taken from classical mechanics i.e. is a form of information equilibrium. Thus for any energy, a quantum bound state has classical energy conservation embedded. The difference is that the additional information from the $\exp(ipx)$ s used in the averaging process is also present. This leads to only certain energy E values being allowed (i.e. a discrete set) and a $W(x)$ linked to $W^*(x)W(x)$ (spatial density) which exhibits humps (not seen in classical mechanics). The form: $KE(x) + V(x) = E_n$ which describes average spatial information for any energy level is identical in classical and quantum mechanics. (Thus one could in principle introduce a $v_{rms}(x)$ from $KE(x)$ and associate this with $p(x)$ classical.)

As a result we argue that the time independent Schrodinger equation is not developed independently of classical mechanical information ideas. The two share the idea of conservation of energy. Thus we argue there is no reason to think of classical mechanics as being the limit of quantum mechanics. If one removes wave behaviour i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ s, the remaining average energy equation (time independent Schrodinger equation) is exactly the classical one at any E . A $v(x)$ then emerges equivalent to $v_{rms}(x)$ from $KE(x)$ in the quantum mechanical equation.

References

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